

The Formation and Stability of Polybromide Derivatives of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part IV. The Hydrodibromides and Hydrotetrabromides of some 1-Dimethylaminobenzthiazoles.

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Since 1-aminobenzthiazole hydrodibromide (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 125) fails to exhibit the paramagnetism to be anticipated on the basis of the odd-electron structure (I) (Aliazam, Hunter and Khan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 708), it has been suggested to us that the compound may possess a nitrogen bromide structure of the type (II).

This formula is, however, quite inadmissible in the light of the behaviour of the substance on pyrolysis and the total absence of evidence of any substitution during its preparation from the hydrobromic acid salt of 1-aminobenzthiazole and bromine (Hunter, *loc. cit.*). Nevertheless, in view of this suggestion, it appeared of interest to re-examine the dibromide of 1-dimethylaminobenzthiazole obtained from *s*-phenyldimethylthiocarbamide and bromine some years ago (Hunter and Styles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1209), in which the possibility of substitution by bromine in the μ -amino group is definitely precluded.

As might be anticipated, the supposed dibromide is actually a hydrodibromide of the dimethylamino base, analogous to the bromo-addition compound of 1-aminobenzthiazole obtained from phenylthiocarbamide under similar conditions (*cf.* Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147).

On more prolonged bromination in presence of excess of the

halogen, *s*-phenyldimethylthiocarbamide gave rise to a hydrotetra-bromide of a monobromo base which yielded 5-bromo-1-dimethylamino-benzthiazole (IV), whose constitution was established by synthesis from *s*-*p*-bromophenyldimethylthiocarbamide (III), on treatment with sulphurous acid (*cf.* Chowdhury, Desai, and Hunter, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1934. 53, 1).

(III)

(IV)

A similar hydrodibromide of 1-dimethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole was also obtained from *s*-*p*-tolylidimethylthiocarbamide, by treatment with bromine under conditions similar to those employed in the case of the phenyl derivative. On more prolonged treatment with excess of bromine, the cyclised product underwent nuclear substitution as in the case already described, yielding a hydrotetrabromide of a base identical with 3-bromo-1-dimethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole (VI) obtained by cyclisation of *s*-*o*-bromo-*p*-tolylidimethylthiocarbamide (V).

(V)

(VI)

Since the formation of hydrodibromides and hydrotetrabromides of aminobenzthiazole bases is no longer explainable on the basis of the existence of even-numbered polybromide ions (*cf.* Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *loc. cit.*), it appears highly probable that these

compounds are complexes of the type $\left[\text{Base, H}^{\oplus} \right]_2 \overbrace{\text{Br}^{\ominus} \text{Br}_2^{\ominus} \text{Br}^{\ominus}}$ and

$\left[\text{Base, H}^{\oplus} \right]_2 \overbrace{\text{Br}^{\ominus} (\text{Br}_2)_3 \text{Br}^{\ominus}}$ respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL.

s-Phenyldimethylthiocarbamide, prepared by treating a solution of phenylthiocarbimide (5 g.) in benzene (25 c.c.) with a 33 % solution of dimethylamine in alcohol (5 c.c.) and heating the mixture, crystallised in needles, m.p. 133° (Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 61, 539).

1-Dimethylaminobenzthiazole hydrodibromide.—A solution of the dimethylthiocarbamide (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was gradually treated with bromine (0.6 c.c.) and the solution was heated on a water-bath under reflux for 5 minutes, transferred to a crystallising basin and concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. On rubbing with a glass rod, the hydrodibromide formed small red crystals which were collected on porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum, m.p. 91-93° (decomp., after previous softening). [Found: Br (total), 48.1; Br (labile), 23.8. $C_9H_{10}N_2S$, HBr(Br) requires Br (total), 47.3; Br (labile), 23.7 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia, the hydrodibromide yielded 1-dimethylaminobenzthiazole which separated from benzene-petroleum in glistening flakes, m.p. 87°. (Found: S, 17.7. Calc. S, 18.0 per cent).

5-Bromo-1-dimethylaminobenzthiazole hydrotetrabromide.—A solution of *s*-phenyldimethylthiocarbamide (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 3 c.c. of chloroform), and the mixture was heated under reflux for 20 minutes and concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. The hydrotetrabromide crystallised in orange red prisms which had m. p. 100° (decomp.) after drying in a vacuum. [Found: Br. (total). 69.0; Br (labile), 41.3. $C_9H_9N_2BrS$, HBr (Br₃) requires Br (total), 69.1; Br (labile), 41.5 per cent). On reduction with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia, the hydrotetrabromide yielded 5-bromo-1-dimethylaminobenzthiazole, which crystallised from petroleum-benzene in stout prisms, m.p. 167°. (Found: Br, 30.9. $C_9H_9N_2BrS$ requires Br, 31.1 per cent).

Synthesis of 5-Bromo-1-dimethylaminobenzthiazole from p-Bromophenylthiocarbimide by way of s-p-bromophenyldimethylthiocarbamide.
(i) *s-p-Bromophenyldimethylthiocarbamide*, prepared from *p*-bromophenylthiocarbimide (2 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) and a 33 % solution of dimethylamine in alcohol (1.2 c.c.), crystallised from benzene in small needles, m.p. 159°. (Found: Br, 30.8. $C_9H_{11}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 30.9 per cent). (ii) A solution of this thiocarbamide (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 3 c.c. of chloroform), and the mixture was heated under reflux for 25 minutes. The product

obtained by removing the solvent in a vacuum at laboratory temperature was reduced with sulphurous acid, basified and recrystallised from petroleum-benzene when 5-bromo-1-dimethylaminobenzthiazole was obtained in stout prisms which had m.p. 167° alone, and when mixed with the specimen obtained by bromination of *s*-phenyldimethylthiocarbamide.

1-Dimethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole hydrodibromide.—A solution of *s-p*-tolyldimethylthiocarbamide (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.5 c.c. dissolved in 2 c.c. of the same solvent) and the solution was heated under reflux for 5 minutes and thereafter concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. The *hydrodibromide* of the 5-methylbenzthiazole formed small orange prisms, m.p. 90° after drying. [Found: Br (total), 44.8; Br (labile), 22.2. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2S$, HBr (Br) requires Br (total), 45.3; Br (labile), 22.6 per cent). On reduction with sulphurous acid, this bromo-addition compound yielded 1-dimethylaminobenzthiazole, which separated from alcohol in small prisms, m.p. 86° (Hunter and Styles, *loc. cit.*).

3-Bromo-1-dimethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole hydrotetrabromide.—A solution of *s-p*-tolyldimethylthiocarbamide (2 g.) in chloroform (15 c.c.) was treated with bromine (2 c.c.) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 20 minutes and thereafter concentrated in a vacuum at laboratory temperature. The *hydrotetrabromide* crystallised in glistening orange red needles, m.p. 95° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 67.2; Br (labile), 40.3. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2BrS$, HBr(Br₃) requires Br (total), 67.6; Br (labile), 40.6 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid the hydrotetrabromide yielded *3-bromo-1-dimethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole*, which crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 169°. (Found: Br, 29.8. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 29.5 per cent).

Synthesis of 3-bromo-1-dimethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole from s-o-bromo-p-tolyldimethylthiocarbamide. *s-o-Bromo-p-tolyldimethylthiocarbamide*, prepared from *o*-bromo-*p*-tolythiocarbimide (2 g.) and dimethylamine in benzene, crystallised in needles, m.p. 158°. (Found: Br, 29.5. $C_{10}H_{13}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 29.3 per cent). On cyclisation by treatment with bromine in the usual way and reduction of the product with sulphurous acid, *3-bromo-1-dimethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole* was obtained which had m.p. 169° alone, and when mixed with the specimen already described.